

Resistance is in the Air: Citizens, science and air pollution

International interdisciplinary symposium

Brussels, 25-26 April 2019

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1 Theme of the symposium

Resistance is in the air. All over the world, awareness of air pollution as a serious matter of concern is growing. This is prominent in the rise of citizen groups claiming their right to clean air, the increasing number of newspaper articles on the subject, and the growing mobilisation across broad ranges of society. At the same time, air pollution is also academically taken up more widely and consistently: an increasing amount of scholarship is looking into the issue from a wide variety of disciplines. Air quality policies are also at a turning point. The growing number of citizen science projects, living labs, crowd-sensing and other similar initiatives contributes to blurring the boundaries between “citizens” and “experts”. This shows the potential of dialogue and collaboration among different actors, but also represents a step towards transcending these categories and making place for promising new ways of thinking about research, action and citizenship. Overall, there is a sense of urgency, rooted in state-of-the-art knowledge about the risks of exposure, the apparent inadequacy of the current legal framework, policy and infrastructural solutions, and the -sometimes distorted- way information on air pollution is collected and disseminated.

It is in this context, this international interdisciplinary symposium will focus on the theme of ‘resistance’, in its diverse possible meanings. The socio-demographic characteristics of people can make them more or less *resistant* to the impacts of air pollution on their health and wellbeing, while their economic situation is likely to exacerbate or help addressing their vulnerability. Historical path dependencies in the urban form and infrastructure, as well as established power relations among groups and stakeholders can make socio-technical systems *resist* change and innovation. Citizens concerned with the health and environmental threats of air pollution may engage in active *resistance* against actual status quo by physically changing their living environment, by exerting political pressure in the streets and in courts, or by taking steps towards alternative metabolisms of air and its pollution. In doing this, they may take resource to existing atmospheric science or contest the state of the art and engage in the co-production of alternative forms of knowledge. However, citizens do not only *resist* air pollution. Citizens also happen to *resist* against prioritising air pollution as a matter of concern and protest against measures to tackle it: referring to social justice, individual freedom or discourses about economic viability and growth, significant groups of citizens claim the ‘need’ or ‘right’ to drive the car or to engage in other polluting practices. Not seldom, it comes to a conflict between citizen groups and other actors with different interests in the air.

2 Context: Les États Généraux de l’Air

The objective of the symposium is to provide a platform for scholarly dialogue and interdisciplinary exchange, among scholars but also with citizens and activists. Bridging the disciplinary gaps, as well as engaging with the larger societal debate, this symposium has the ambition to urge political agenda-setting by pushing reflection on strategies and pathways to more ambitious and broadly supported air quality regulations.

In this regard, the symposium is part of a larger event, which includes a citizen’s day as a forum for societal dialogue and a hackathon for cleaner air through open data mining and manipulation. Scholars who participate in the academic conference are most welcome to also participate in the other activities of the event. Similarly, we will invite the broader public to participate in selected sessions during the academic conference. The event as a whole will provide a forum for critical debate across a range of perspectives on air pollution, will raise awareness about its impact on health and on the environment, learn and exchange about socio-ecological future alternatives and strategies towards change, and will help bridging the gap between science, lived experience, policy and practice

4 Scientific supervision & organisation

- Coordinator: Nicola da Schio (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research)
- Tom Bauler (Université Libre de Bruxelles, IGEAT)
- Catherine Bouland (Université Libre de Bruxelles, CRSET)
- Kobe Boussauw (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research)
- Nicola da Schio (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research)
- Bas de Geus (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, MFYS & MOBI)
- Evi Dons (Hasselt University, Centre for Environmental Sciences)
- Koos Fransen (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research)
- Michel Hubert (Université Saint-Louis – Bruxelles, IRIB)
- Anneleen Kenis (FWO, King's College London)
- Maarten Loopmans (KU Leuven)
- Delphine Misonne (FNRS, Université Saint-Louis – Bruxelles, CEDRE)
- Joren Sansen (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research)
- Bas van Heur (Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research)
- Romain Weikmans (FNRS Université Libre de Bruxelles, IGEAT)

5 Practicalities

The symposium is hosted at PianoFabriek, Rue du Fort Straat 35, Saint Gilles, Brussels

Registration requested: <https://www.brusselsair.org/resistance-in-the-air/registration/>

Fee 120 euro for 2 days (reduction for civil society, master's & bachelor's students, 15 euros per day)
The fee covers the venue, lunches and refreshments on both days. Travel costs and accommodation in Brussels are not included.

For more information, contact: Nicola da Schio (ndaschio@vub.be)

Etats Generaux de l'Air de Bruxelles

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Unmask my City – doctors urging for clean air in our European cities

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Just like the anti-tobacco campaigns of the late 20th century, doctors are sounding alarms about the health risks of poor air quality in our cities. Air pollution is now responsible for over 6.5 million premature deaths per year. Health experts are dedicated to improving the health of patients and communities. Improving air quality and reducing emissions in our cities will save millions of lives and improve health outcomes for billions of people. Unmask My City calls on decision makers to adopt policies and programmes to meet the World Health Organisation's air quality guidelines.